

e.g. beryllium, zirconium(IV) and germanium (sodium fluoride); thorium, scandium, indium(III) and bismuth (ascorbic acid); yttrium, titanium, gallium and cerium(IV) (tartaric acid) and silver (thiourea). The interferences of some of the ions were removed by prior extraction with suitable extractants (1) as shown in brackets; gold (diethyl ether), cobalt (1-nitroso-2-naphthol), nickel (dimethylglyoxine), lead (2-thenoyl-trifluoroacetone) and palladium, copper(II) and mercury(II) (thiobenzoylacetone).

From ten determinations with 10 μg . of zinc, the absorbance was 0.530 ± 0.01 . The standard deviation was $\pm 1.03\%$.

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Kinetic Evidence for Steric Enhancement of Resonance**

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THE phenomenon of steric enhancement of resonance was discovered by Baliah and Uma¹ while studying the electric dipole moments of some substituted anisoles and acetophenones. The results obtained from our present studies of the kinetics of oxidation of some

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substituted phenyl methyl sulphoxides with chloramine-T support this concept.

Experimental

Chloramine-T used was of AnalaR grade (BDH). The purity of each compound was tested by TLC. The kinetics of the reaction was followed by iodometric estimation of chloramine-T in a measured aliquot of the reaction mixture at various time intervals. Phenyl methyl sulphone was found to be the reaction product polarographically.

Results and Discussion

The kinetic data for the oxidation of phenyl methyl sulphoxides with chloramine-T are given in Table 1. *p*-Methoxyphenyl methyl sulphoxide undergoes oxidation 3.1 times faster than phenyl methyl sulphoxide.

TABLE 1—OXIDATION OF PHENYL METHYL SULPHOXIDES BY CHLORAMINE-T IN BUFFERED ETHANOL (1:1 v/v; pH=7.3)

Substrate	$k_2 \times 10^3$ $1. \text{mol}^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1}$
Phenyl methyl sulphoxide	4.34
3-Tolyl methyl sulphoxide	5.99
4-Methoxyphenyl methyl sulphoxide	13.45
4-Methoxy-3-methylphenyl methyl sulphoxide	20.54
4-Methoxy-3,5-dimethylphenyl methyl sulphoxide	8.80

m-Tolyl methyl sulphoxide also undergoes oxidation 1.4 times faster than phenyl methyl sulphoxide. The rate of oxidation of 4-methoxy-3-methylphenyl methyl sulphoxide is significantly higher than that of 4-methoxyphenyl methyl sulphoxide. This increase in rate is not solely due to the 3-methyl group, because the observed rate constant of 4-methoxy-3-methylphenyl methyl sulphoxide ($20.54 \times 10^{-3} \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$) is 11% higher than the value ($18.57 \times 10^{-3} \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$) predicted on the basis of additivity principle². This appreciable difference between the observed and the calculated rate is significant because 3-methyl group does not sterically inhibit the resonance interaction of the *p*-OCH₃ group with the aromatic ring but enhances it. This can be explained by assuming a trans orientation of the methoxy group to the 3-methyl group increasing the probability of its attaining planarity with the aromatic ring due to restricted rotation.

If a single substituent ortho to the -OCH₃ group enhances its resonance interaction with the para substituents, two ortho substituents should cause steric inhibition of resonance, because the two ortho substituents will prevent the -OCH₃ group from attaining planarity with the benzene ring and hinder conjugation with the ring. A comparison of the rate constant calculated for 4-methoxy-3, 5-dimethylphenyl methyl

sulphoxide (25.62×10^{-2} l. mol⁻¹ sec⁻¹) with the observed rate constant (8.80×10^{-2} l. mol⁻¹ sec⁻¹) indicates such a steric inhibition of resonance.

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Preparation of 2, 6-Anhydro-L-Gulose

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1-Deoxy-Nitro-L-gulitol was prepared by a modification of the procedure of Sowden and Fischer¹. This was then anhydriized by pyrolysis to form a Carbohydrate Anhydronitroalcohol, 2,6-anhydro-1-deoxy-1-nitro-L-gulitol which is the optical isomer of the compound reported earlier². 2, 6-anhydro-1-deoxy-1-nitro-L-gulitol was then subjected to the Nef reaction with sulphuric acid to form 2, 6-Anhydro-L-Gulose.

Experimental

Anhydriization of 1-Deoxy-1-Nitro-L-Gulitol to 2,6-Anhydro-1-Deoxy-1-Nitro-L-Gulitol.

1-Deoxy-1-nitro-L-gulitol (10g) was heated in an oven at 90° for 16 hours. The product was dissolved by 95% ethanol by heating in a steam bath and then allowed to cool. 2, 6-Anhydro-1-deoxy-1-nitro-L-gulitol crystallised out (1.3 g.). The mother liquor was evaporated to a solid which on similar treatment as above, yielded another batch (0.8 g.) of the same product. M. P. 166° [α]_D = 8.7°. Anal. found, C=37.6%; H=5.80% and N=7.45%; Calc. for C₆H₁₁O₆N; C=37.3%; H=5.69% and N=7.2%.

Conversion of 2, 6-Anhydro-1-Deoxy-1-Nitro-L-Gulitol to 2, 6-Anhydro-L-Gulose.

2, 6-Anhydro-1-deoxy-1-nitro-L-gulitol (0.8 g.) was heated with (1:1) H₂SO₄ for 2 hours. The excess acid was neutralised with ion exchange resin. The resulting solution was concentrated and crystallised from 95% ethanol when 2, 6-anhydro-L-gulose (0.74 g.) separated out. M. p. 136°; Anal. found, C=44.70%, H=6.40%; calc. for C₆H₁₀O₅, C=44.44% and H=9.17%.

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Isolation and Identification of Pigments of the Flowers of *Clitoria ternatea*

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BOTH the blue and white parts of the fresh flowers (1.5 kg) of *Clitoria ternatea* (Leguminosae) were extracted separately with 1% methanolic HCl. From the extract of blue parts three compounds A, B and C were isolated but the extract of white parts furnished only compound C in reasonable yield. The isolation of these compounds were done by paper chromatography (descending) using 40×20 cm What man No. 1 filter papers and n-butanol : acetic acid ; water (4 : 1 : 5) as developing solvent. The R_f values were 0.21, 0.38 and 0.87 for A, B and C respectively. The strips with different bands were cut out and eluted with 95% ethanol. The eluates were concentrated under reduced pressure and purified by precipitating with petroleum ether and repeated crystallisations.

The dark red compound A, C₂₇H₃₁O₁₆Cl (250 mg), gave all the colour tests of anthocyanins. On hydrolysis with 20% HCl, it yielded glucose (mp, mmp, chromatography and osazone) and an aglycone which was identified as cyanidine chloride by colour reactions, alkali degradation and UV spectral analysis in presence of specific reagents^{1,2,3}. Finally, the identity of compound A with cyanin chloride was established by direct comparison (UV, PC) with the authentic sample obtained from red roses.

Compound B (28 mg) was also recognised to be an anthocyanin from colour tests. Its structural studies could not be done due to paucity of the material.

The yellow compound C (175 mg), C₁₅H₁₀O₆, m.p. 277°, was found to be a flavonol. It formed a tetraacetate, m.p. 116°. The positions of hydroxy groups were settled to be 3,5,7 and 4' by colour reactions, degradation studies and spectral analysis. Thus the structure of C was established as 3,5,7, and 4'-tetrahydroxy flavone i.e., kaempferol, which was further confirmed by co-chromatography with authentic sample obtained from blue delphinium flowers.

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